

NEW MATERIALS CONCEPTS FOR ULTRA-LIGHTWEIGHT FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

Dr. M. Akonda; Prof. C. A. Lawrence; Dr. M. Mahmoudi;
 Dr. H. M. EL-Dessouky; Mr.A.Thomas
 Centre for Technical Textiles; ADCOM; University of Leeds
 Leeds, LS2 9JT, UK

Summary

Composite materials are today widely used in a broad range of components for automotive, aerospace, marine, electrical energy generation and architectural structures. Carbon fibre composite (CRP) is the preferred material for lightweight and high performance. There is, however, growing concern among some composites manufacturers that the growth in demand for the material will continue to outstrip the expansion of fibre production capacity as it has for the past few years with the result of a continued tightening of supplies and higher prices. Market analysis would tend to indicate that supply, if not already overtaken by demand, will do so before the end of 2009. This situation presents the opportunity for new ways of utilising carbon fibres more efficiently by development of new textile pre-forms, particularly for laminated structures employing thermoplastic resins.

The figure below lists 10 areas identified by the Composite Thematic Network on “The Future of Composites in Transport”. The highlighted ones are those most relevant to the development of new textile pre-forms for thermoplastic laminate structures.

Fig.1 Areas for Product Development Tows

Fig.2 Conventional & Spread

Woven spread-tow pre-forms have the potential to meet the demand for new manufacturing methods of composite laminates to reduce product cost, provide lighter weight components and improved crashworthiness. Carbon fibre producers usually provide relatively large size tows (ie. 12k, 24k, etc) for CRP laminates in order to reduce production cost. The constituent fibres of the tows should be preferably arranged

to enable good impregnation of the resin. However, carbon fibre tow is usually compacted by the application of sizing finish. Impregnation then becomes difficult by viscose matrix resins such as thermoplastics. Spreading the tow to facilitate better impregnation is therefore of much interest, (See Fig.2)but to do so effectively without damaging the carbon fibre filaments may require new manufacturing technologies.

This presentation will describe a pneumatic process for spreading reinforcing fibre tows and the weaving of such tows into lightweight fabrics for CRP laminates. The near negligible crimp in the spread tow fabric enables significant improvements on modulus compared with conventional woven fabrics and facilitates the production of laminates from ultra thin laminas of the order of 0.05mm thickness. Although CRP sheets are extensively used for laminates, the propensity for delamination or separation of the laminas is still a major problem. According to Kageyama's theory on transverse lamina cracking, laminates constructed from thin laminas will give the best energy absorption from impact. Spread tow fabrics therefore offer the opportunity for much improved crashworthiness.

The information presented will attempt to convey the enhanced micromechanics that can be obtained from spread-tow laminates and will include symmetric, antisymmetric and asymmetric geometries.

When taking to account cutting and shaping pre-forms, of the order of 30% to 40% of carbon fibre is wasted during composite manufacture. This does not account for end-of-life components, the importance of which will grow over the next 5 to 15 years with the increasing environmental concerns. The potential new markets for new products developed from recycled carbon fibre, is therefore attracting attention from manufacturers throughout the supply chain. The use of recycled fibre as interlaminar layers is of interest and the manufacture and performance of such materials, comprising sandwich layers of spread-tow and re-cycled carbon fibre/thermoplastic resin blends, will be discussed.

The presentation will conclude with a review of how spread-tow recycled-carbon-fibre thermoplastic laminates meets the challenge for lightweighting and crashworthiness, and the potential applications for such new materials.